

Homeopathic poisoning of RAG systems

Boussad Addad^[0000-0001-7951-1273] and Katarzyna Kapusta^[0000-0003-0963-4782]

CortAix Lab, Thales Group, France
{surname.name}@thalesgroup.com

Abstract. Despite their remarkable success and wide use in many applications, large language models (LLMs) suffer from some limitations like vulnerability to some attacks (e.g. prompt injection) and drop in performance due to lack of up-to-date knowledge, and hallucinations. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is currently one of the most promising techniques to mitigate such issues. In short, a RAG augments each prompt using a relevant context from an external knowledge database. Often, the context is a set of texts (top-k) that are the most similar to the request. While the issue of hallucinations is largely reduced, RAG augments at the same time the attack surface on the whole system. An attacker may poison the knowledge database by injecting bad or misleading information. In this paper, we introduce HOPRAG, a subtle, but very efficient, poisoning technique that consists in adding a suffix (or prefix) of only few tokens (sub-words) to any given text to raise (or decrease) its similarity with a prompt and therefore be used (or avoid being used) as context by RAG to answer. Our results show that with only three injected tokens, we cause a similarity shift of 0.4 on average.

Keywords: LLM, RAG, Poisoning.

1 Introduction

Given their remarkable capabilities, large language models (LLMs) such as GPT-3.5, GPT-4, Claude, and Gemini are widely deployed in various types of chatbots. Nevertheless, these models cannot answer correctly questions regarding recent events due to the cutoff date for their training data. The first version of ChatGPT for instance was limited to data up to September 2021. LLM have also trouble answering questions related to topics covered with limited amount of data in the training dataset. Consequently, they may hallucinate – provide incorrect answers that seems correct - when providing a response about such a topic [1].

One can always retrain or fine-tune a LLM with fresher data but this is a heavy and costly process, making frequent updates a burden [2]. This is a critical drawback in using LLM in fast evolving domains like the news or scientific research.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [3], [4] boosts the LLM knowledge with an external database. It is the go-to solution to improve the LLM’s output quality and reduce hallucinations. The standard RAG architecture is composed of a knowledge base, a LLM and a retriever. The processing flow in a RAG is depicted

in Figure. 1. First of all, the external knowledge sources are encoded using an embedding model to obtain a high dimension vector for each text. This results in the whole database being represented in a vector store. The embedding model is trained in a way that all the texts that are semantically similar are encoded using similar vectors [5]. Therefore, every time a user sends a request to the LLM, the retriever does the following: the prompt is encoded using the same embedding model to obtain a vector that is compared to all the elements of the vector store. The top-k vectors that are most similar to it (e.g. via cosine similarity) are selected. The corresponding texts are therefore used as a relevant context to augment the original prompt. The augmented prompt is finally used by the LLM to generate an answer to the user request.

Fig. 1. RAG architecture and processing flow steps.

With regard to RAG, the ongoing studies are focusing on improving the performance of the retriever [6], [7]. However, security related issues of RAG have so far attracted little attention. Yet, the attack surface is augmented in RAG comparing to LLM, as an attacker may poison the database by injecting bad or misleading information. In this paper, we introduce HOPRAG, a subtle poisoning technique that consists in adding a suffix (or prefix) of only few tokens (sub-words) to any given text to raise (or decrease) its similarity with a prompt and therefore be used (or avoid being used) as context by RAG to answer a request.

2 Background and related work

Different studies were published on several types of attacks targeting LLM like model weights stealing [8], training data leakage [9], backdoors [10], and prompt injection [11], [12] that aim at making the LLM misbehave as desired by the attacker. One of such attacks that attracted much focus in literature is jailbreaking that aim to break the alignment of LLMs, even the toughest ones like GPT-4, Claude and Gemini. When asked a question like “How to build a bomb”, these aligned models do not answer and provide an excuse like “I am sorry, as a responsible AI I cannot...”. However, with

prompts crafted in some way, adding for instance an optimized suffix [13], these LLM would answer the forbidden questions.

While data poisoning during the training phase is a thoroughly covered topic [14], [15], to the best of our knowledge, the security of RAG remains almost unexplored. As writing the current paper, an attack named PoisonedRAG was published [16].

Our contribution: In this work, we introduce HOPRAG (Homeopathic Poisoning of RAG) that successfully poisons the RAG by injecting few tokens to a given targeted answer in the form of a short suffix (or prefix). Thanks to limiting the length of the suffix/prefix, the answer of the LLM can be made according to the original text content. Also, contrary to PoisonedRAG, no proxy LLM is needed during the attack.

3 Problem formulation and attack design

3.1 Threat model

We characterize the threat model with respect to two aspects:

Attacker’s goal: the malevolent goal of attacker in the real world could be spreading disinformation, biasing LLM answers towards negative or positive views on products or even people, propagating financial misinformation, etc.

In a formal way, an attacker selects from a database D a desired context C to be used by the LLM to answer (let us call this the *target context*) for a given question Q (let us call it *target question*). The context may be constituted of several texts (top-k) from the database but for the sake of simplicity (without loss of generality as the attack may target all the texts, one after another) we will suppose C to refer to one text.

While the goal of an attacker is to favor some context to be used by the LLM, one can also has a goal of disfavoring a given context and avoid being used. So, we will consider both cases while call the first a *similarity attack* and the second a *dissimilarity attack*.

Attacker’s knowledge: For the retriever we choose a white-box threat model, where an attacker has full access to the embedding model. We motivated this by the fact that many embedding models are open source while being competitive with the best closed source ones (even better than the OpenAI ada model¹). We also suppose that the attacker can influence the content of the knowledge database in one way or another. He may have a direct access to the database (e.g. insider) or indirect access by publishing content on the Internet (e.g. on a forum) that will be later stored into the database.

3.2 Design of HOPRAG

Let us assume that the embedding model used by the retriever is M and the considered similarity criterion is L . So, the vector of a text t is $V_t = M(t)$ and the similarity between two vectors V_1 and V_2 is $D(V_1, V_2)$. For a target question Q and target context C , the

¹ See the MTEB benchmark available at : <https://huggingface.co/spaces/mteb/leaderboard>

goal is to find a suffix S so that vectors $V_{(C+S)}$ and V_Q are similar (similarity attack) or dissimilar (dissimilarity attack). The design of the attack is therefore equivalent to the resolution of an optimization problem where one has to maximize $D(V_{(C+S)}, V_Q)$ in the case of similarity attack and minimize $D(V_{(C+S)}, V_Q)$ in case of dissimilarity attack. Two examples of this process are given in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Examples of HOPRAG poisoning attacks; similarity (left) and dissimilarity attack (right).

To solve the optimization problem, we use gradient descent following a similar approach from [16], used there for designing prompt injection attacks. The same method was originally introduced in [17] as HotFlip and applied for attacking NLP classification models (not LLM). A pseudocode of the algorithm of HOPRAG similarity attack is shown below. The code of the dissimilarity attack is quite the same. We only need to change the sign of the loss and invert the comparison (line 11).

Algorithm: HOPRAG similarity attack

```

1  Input: target question  $Q$ , target context  $C$ , Suffix length  $L$ , number of top gradients  $K$ , number of
2  suffix candidates  $F$ , number of optimization iterations  $N$ 
3  Output: optimized suffix  $S$ 
4   $S \leftarrow$  "!!!! ... !" # suffix length equal to  $L$ 
5   $D_{\min} = 10000$ 
6  for  $k=1, \dots, N$  do
7       $\text{grads} \leftarrow$  CalculateGradients( $D(V_{(C+S)}, V_Q)$ )
8       $\text{top\_indices} \leftarrow$  SelectTopGradientsIndices( $\text{grads}, K$ )
9       $\text{suffix\_candidates} \leftarrow$  HotFlip( $S, \text{top\_indices}, F$ )
10     for  $SC$  in  $\text{suffix\_candidates}$  do
11         if  $D(V_{(C+SC)}, V_Q) < D_{\min}$  do
12              $S \leftarrow SC$ 
13              $D_{\min} = D(V_{(C+SC)}, V_Q)$ 
14         end for
15     end for
16 return  $S$ 

```

4 Experiment

4.1 Methodology and settings

To perform our experiments, we used QUORA dataset, constituted of 400,000 texts from the forum website of the same name, and used for many research studies.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of HOPRAG attack, we considered the worst-case scenarios for both similarity and dissimilarity attacks. For the first [Similarity] attack, we randomly selected 1000 samples from the dataset and for each sample we looked for the most dissimilar text from the dataset. Likewise, we formed 1000 couples of texts that are semantically very different and tried to make them similar with the attack. For the second attack [Dissimilarity], instead of selecting similar texts to form couples, we randomly extracted 2000 texts from the dataset and tried to make each text dissimilar to a copy of itself. This evaluation method obviously makes things harder but is a good way to assess HOPRAG effectiveness even with extreme cases.

The considered criterion in our experiments is the mean difference (shift) of similarity over all the samples before and after adding the suffixes. We repeated the experiments using different suffix lengths from {1, 3, 5, 10} tokens to study the influence of this parameter on the similarity shift and therefore on the attacks effectiveness. The other important parameter we considered was the number steps of the optimization process (number of gradient descents). The evolution of the similarity shifts as function of it for dissimilarity and similarity attacks are displayed on Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively.

To show that the similarity change is not due to injecting more tokens in the text rather than HOPRAG, we considered an attack that consists in adding random tokens (Fig. 3). We ran all the experiments using an open-source embedding model called all-MiniLM-L12-v2. This model is not as big as the closed models, but displays impressive performance. Therefore, this model is well suited for research². We ran the experiments using a computer with 16G RAM and a GPU of type RTX-2080.

Fig. 3. Poisoning baseline: we inject random tokens into the context and observe their impact on the similarity/dissimilarity in comparison to the given question.

4.2 Discussion of the results

First, we demonstrate that the attack is very fast to perform. It takes less than a second to only few seconds. Regarding the curves, here are the key results:

- The baseline attack using injection of random tokens (Fig. 3) is not effective at all in the case of similarity attack as the curve remains flat and close to zero even when the maximum number of tokens ($L = 10$) we considered is injected. With regard to the

² All the model related information can be found here : <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L12-v2>

dissimilarity attack, it is much better but the shift remains smaller than 0.4 even when $L = 10$. This result was, at least qualitatively, expected. Indeed, when injecting tokens into a text, we create some dilution of the text tokens and therefore semantically move away from the original meaning.

Fig. 4. Mean difference similarity evolution over the optimization process in the dissimilarity attack setting (L is suffix length).

Fig. 5. Mean difference similarity evolution over the optimization process in the similarity attack (L is suffix length).

- The HOPRAG dissimilarity attack (Fig. 4) is effective and does much better than random injection, causing a shift of more than 0.4 even with a suffix of only 3 tokens and after only 10 optimization iterations. With a suffix of length $L = 10$, the shift is greater than 0.8. Obviously, this high value is likely to alter the top-k ranking of a RAG and therefore influence deeply the LLM answers.

- The HOPRAG similarity attack (Fig. 5) is also effective and causes an average shift of 0.4 towards the targets with only very limited length suffixes ($L = 3$). This proves that for a given request, we can target any context from the knowledge database, even one that is semantically very far, to be used by the LLM to provide an answer. The consequence of such poisoning attack is obviously critical as the attacker can bias the answers of the LLM/RAG as he desires without any difficulty. Moreover, the required time and hardware means are within everyone's reach to apply HOPRAG.

5 Conclusion and future work

We first introduce the novel concept of similarity/dissimilarity attack in RAG systems. We propose and implement the HOPRAG attack, which modifies effectively the similarity/dissimilarity between the RAG's context and a given query by injecting short but very efficient suffixes to the context.

While HOPRAG focused in the current work on adding a suffix to the context to change the top-k ranking of the RAG retriever, exactly the same principle can be applied on the prompt side. Such attack is even easier, as no access to the database is required.

As future work, we plan to extend the HOPRAG threat model to a black-box setting. We would also like to investigate defenses against RAG's poisoning attacks.

Acknowledgments.

This work was supported by the European Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101070599 (SecOPERA).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Z. Ji, N. Lee, R. Frieske, T. Yu, D. Su, Y. Xu, E. Ishii, Y. J. Bang, A. Madotto, and P. Fung, "Survey of hallucination in natural language generation," *ACM Computing Surveys*, 2023.
2. O. Ovadia, M. Brief, M. Mishaeli, and O. Elisha, "Fine-tuning or retrieval? comparing knowledge injection in llms," *arXiv*, 2023.
3. P. Lewis, E. Perez, A. Piktus, F. Petroni, V. Karpukhin, N. Goyal, H. Küttler, M. Lewis, W.-t. Yih, T. Rocktäschel et al., "Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive nlp tasks," *NeurIPS*, 2020.
4. S. Borgeaud, A. Mensch, J. Hoffmann, T. Cai, E. Rutherford, K. Millican, G. B. Van Den Driessche, J.-B. Lespiau, B. Damoc, A. Clark et al., "Improving language models by retrieving from trillions of tokens," in *ICML*, 2022.
5. Tianyu Gao, Xingcheng Yao, and Danqi Chen, Simcse: Simple contrastive learning of sentence embeddings. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.08821*.
6. L. Xiong, C. Xiong, Y. Li, K.-F. Tang, J. Liu, P. N. Bennett, J. Ahmed, and A. Overwijk, Approximate nearest neighbor negative contrastive learning for dense text retrieval, in *ICLR*, 2021.
7. Z. Peng, X. Wu, and Y. Fang, Soft prompt tuning for augmenting dense retrieval with large language models, *arXiv:2307.08303v4*.
8. N. Carlini, D. Paleka, K-Dj Dvijotham, T. Steinke, J. Hayase, A-F. Cooper, K. Lee, M. Jagielski, M. Nasr, A. Conmy, E. Wallace, D. Rolnick, F. Tramèr, Stealing Part of a Production Language Model, *arXiv:2403.06634v1*.
9. Jaydeep Borkar, What can we learn from Data Leakage and Unlearning for Law?, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.10476>.
10. Yingqi Liu¹, Guangyu Shen, Guanhong Tao, Shengwei An, Shiqing Ma, Xiangyu Zhang, PICCOLO : Exposing Complex Backdoors in NLP Transformer Models, *SP22*.
11. P. Chao, A. Robey, E. Dobriban, H. Hassani, G-J. Pappas, E. Wong, Jailbreaking Black Box Large Language Models in Twenty Queries, *arXiv:2310.08419v2*.
12. X. Liu, N. Xu, M. Chen, C. Xiao, AUTODAN: Generating stealthy jailbreak prompts on aligned large language models, *arXiv:2310.04451v1*.
13. A. Zou, Z. Wang, J-Z. Kolter, M Fredrikson, Universal and Transferable Adversarial Attacks on Aligned Language Models, *arXiv:2307.15043v1*.
14. B. Biggio, B. Nelson, and P. Laskov, "Poisoning attacks against support vector machines," in *ICML*, 2012.
15. A. Shafahi, W. R. Huang, M. Najibi, O. Suciuc, C. Studer, T. Dumitras, and T. Goldstein, "Poison frogs! targeted clean-label poisoning attacks on neural networks," in *NeurIPS*, 2018.
16. W. Zou, R. Geng, B. Wang, J. Jia, PoisonedRAG: Knowledge Poisoning Attacks to RAG of Large Language Models, *arXiv:2402.07867v1*.
17. J. Ebrahimi, A. Rao, D. Lowd, and D. Dou, "Hotflip: White-box adversarial examples for text classification," in *ACL*, 2018.